

Yogic Vision in the *Rāmāyaṇa* – A Study through *Pātañjali* and *Vāsiṣṭha***Smt. Charumathy. B**

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Abstract

The Indian epics and *Purāṇas* are vast repositories of spiritual wisdom, science and technology, and the art of living. One such exploration of yogic insight through an epic is the analysis of the *Rāmāyaṇa* in the light of *Pātañjali's Yoga Sūtras* and Sage *Vāsiṣṭha's* teachings. This article explores the profound interconnections between the *Rāmāyaṇa*, the teachings of Sage *Vāsiṣṭha*, and *Pātañjali's Yoga Sūtras (PYS)*, shedding light on the subtle yogic undercurrents that permeate the epic. Through episodes involving sages like *Nārada* and *Vāsiṣṭha*, divine beings like *Kāmadhenu*, and central characters like *Rāma*, *Sītā* and *Hanumān*, it reveals how yogic principles such as *tapas*, *svādhyāya*, *īśvara-praṇidhāna*, *kāmarūpa siddhi*, and *bhūta-jaya* manifest as inner discipline, supernatural perception, and divine strength. The article aims to present the *Rāmāyaṇa* not just as a spiritual narrative but as a living embodiment of yogic realization, offering timeless guidance for seekers on the path of self-mastery over the mind and paving the way for liberation.

Key words

Rāmāyaṇa, *Yoga Sūtras*, *Vāsiṣṭha*, *Pātañjali's Yoga Sūtras (PYS)*, *tapas*, *svādhyāya*, *īśvara-praṇidhāna*, *kāmarūpa siddhi*, *bhūta-jaya*, *Sītā*, *Hanumān*, yogic philosophy, Indian epic, spiritual discipline

Nārada, the ideal Kriyā-Yogin.

तपःस्वाध्यायनिरतं तपस्वी वाग्विदां वरम् ।

नारदं परिप्रच्छ वाल्मीकिर्मुनिपुङ्गवम् ॥ १-१-१

The ascetic *Vālmīki* asked *Nārada*, who was highly accomplished in religious austerities and Vedic study, and renowned as the most eloquent of sages.

Yogic action consists of three components: discipline (*tapas*), self-study (*svādhyāya*), and orientation towards the ideal of pure awareness or devotion to God (*īśvara-praṇidhāna*).

तपःस्वाध्यायेश्वरप्रणिधानानि क्रियायोगः ॥ २.१॥

These three – penance, study, and surrendering of the fruits of action to God, together constitute *Kriyā-Yoga*, as defined in *Pātañjali's Yoga Sūtras (PYS)* (2.1).

Sage *Nārada* is referred to by *Vālmīki* as a *yogin* who practiced this form of *Kriyā-Yoga*. It represents the preparatory stage of Yoga.

शौचसंतोषतपःस्वाध्यायेश्वरप्रणिधानानि नियमाः ॥ २.३२॥

From this verse, we can also see that these three are part of the *Niyamas* mentioned by *Patañjali* in *Yoga Śāstra*.

Valmiki's Yoga Drṣṭi:

स्वाध्यायाद् इष्टदेवतासंप्रयोगः ॥ २.४४॥

Self-study leads to communion with one's chosen or desired deity. This concept explains why Sage *Nārada* assures *Vālmīki* that (through yogic vision) he can perceive the entire life of *Rāma*.

अथ सरसिजयोनेराज्ञया रामवृत्तं करबदरसमानं प्रेक्ष्य दृष्ट्या प्रतीच्या ।

शुभमतनुत काव्यं स्वादु रामायणाख्यं मधुमयफणितीनां मार्गदर्शी महर्षिः ॥

This verse from the *Campū Rāmāyaṇa* conveys how *Vālmīki*, by the command of *Brahmā* (the lotus-born), sees the entire biography of *Rāma* (through his *yoga drṣṭi*).

ततः पश्यति धर्मात्मा तत्सर्वं योगमास्थितः ।

पुरा यत्तत्र निर्वृत्तं पाणावामलकं यथा ॥1.3.6॥

Then, the righteous *Vālmīki*, established in yoga, saw all that had happened in the past—clearly, like an *āmalaka* fruit placed in the palm of his hand.

Sampāti's Yogic vision:

Although *Sampāti* was a vulture; and vultures, by their very nature, possess extraordinary long-distance vision, it is a scientifically established fact that they can spot a three-foot-long carcass from over four miles away (approximately 6 kilometers). However, *Sampāti* was able to see *Sītā Devī* sitting in the *Aśoka Vana*, which was located 100 *yojanas* away. Since one *yojana* is roughly 8 kilometers, this means *Sampāti* saw something nearly 800 kilometers away, an impossible feat by natural sight alone.

This extraordinary vision can only be explained through yogic insight, a supernormal power described in *PYS*.

ततः प्रातिभश्रावणवेदनादर्शास्वादवार्ता जायन्ते ॥3.36॥

From that knowledge (born of perfect discipline), there arises intuitive perception (*prātibha*), supernormal hearing (*śravaṇa*), touch (*vedanā*), sight (*adarśa*), taste (*āsvāda*), and smell (*vārtā*).

Thus, *Sampāti*'s ability was not ordinary. It should have been the result of deep yogic perception. In the *Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa (Kishkindhā Kāṇḍa)*, *Sampāti* describes what he has seen:

तां तु सीतामहं मन्ये रामस्य परिकीर्तनात्।

श्रूयतां मे कथयतो निलयं तस्य रक्षसः ॥4.58.18॥

Since she was uttering *Rāma*'s name, I believe she is *Sītā*. Now hear from me the location of the demon's dwelling.

पुत्रो विश्रवस स्साक्षाद्भ्राता वैश्रवणस्य च।

अध्यास्ते नगरीं लङ्कां रावणो नाम राक्षसः ॥4.58.19॥

Rāvaṇa, the son of *Viśravas* and half-brother of *Kubera* (*Vaiśravaṇa*), resides in the city of *Laṅkā*.

इतो द्वीपस्समुद्रस्य सम्पूर्णे शतयोजने।

तस्मिन्लङ्कापुरी रम्या निर्मिता विश्वकर्मणा ॥4.58.20॥

That beautiful city of *Laṅkā* lies across the sea, a full hundred *yojanas* from here. It was constructed by *Viśvakarma*.

जाम्बूनदमयैद्वारैश्चित्रैः काञ्चनवेदिकैः।

प्रासादैर्हेमवर्णैश्च महद्भिः सुसमा कृता ॥4.58.21॥

प्राकारेणार्कवर्णेन महता च समान्विता॥

With golden gates, decorative platforms, massive golden-hued mansions, and a boundary wall as radiant as the Sun, *Laṅkā* is splendidly built.

तस्यां वसति वैदेही दीना कौशेयवासिनी॥

रावणान्तःपुरे रुद्धा राक्षसीभिस्सुरक्षिता॥

जनकस्यात्मजां राज्ञस्तत्र द्रक्ष्यथ मैथिलीम्॥4.58.22–23॥

In that city dwells the sorrowful *Sītā*, clad in silk, held captive in *Rāvaṇa*'s inner quarters, guarded closely by demonesses. There, you will see the daughter of King *Janaka*, the princess of *Mithilā*.

Kāmadhenu's Yogic Power:

An analysis based on the *PYS* offers insights into the extraordinary powers that can arise from yogic mastery, especially over the *bhūtas* (elements).

त्रयमेकत्र संयमः ॥ 3.4 ॥

The three practices—*dhāraṇā* (concentration), *dhyāna* (meditation), and *samādhi* (absorption)—when applied together on the same object, are called *samyama*.

स्थूलस्वरूपसूक्ष्मान्वयार्थवत्त्वसंयमाद्भूतजयः ॥ 3.44 ॥

By performing *samyama* on the five forms of the elements – *sthūla* (gross), *svarūpa* (essential nature), *sūkṣma* (subtle), *anvaya* (interconnectedness), and *arthavattva* (purpose) – one attains mastery over those elements.

In practical terms, through *samyama*, the yogi perceives and controls the visible, subtle, hidden, and distant aspects of the material world:

sthūla – gross or physical

svarūpa – essential nature

sūkṣma – subtle

avyavahita – not directly accessible

viprakṛṣṭa – far or distant

jñāna – perception or knowledge

बलेषु हस्तिबलादीनि || 3.24 ||

By performing *samyama* on strength (e.g., the strength of an elephant), the yogi gains access to that very power.

This philosophical foundation helps us understand the divine powers exhibited by *Kāmadhenu*, the celestial wish-fulfilling cow, in the *Rāmāyaṇa*. When Sage *Viśvāmitra* attacked with powerful weapons, Sage *Vasiṣṭha* invoked *Kāmadhenu*'s yogic capabilities:

ततस्तानाकुलान् दृष्ट्वा विश्वामित्रास्त्रमोहितान्।

वसिष्ठश्चोदयामास कामधुक् सृज योगतः॥1.55.1॥

Seeing his forces tormented and bewildered by *Viśvāmitra*'s *astras* (weapons), *Vasiṣṭha* instructed *Kāmadhenu* - 'Create additional forces through your yogic power.'

तस्या हुम्भारवाज्जाताः काम्बोजा रविसन्निभाः।

ऊधसस्त्वथ सञ्जाताः पल्लवाशशस्त्रपाणयः॥1.55.2॥

योनिदेशाञ्च यवनाशशकृद्देशाच्छका तथा।

रोमकूपेषु च म्लेच्छा हारीतास्किरातकाः॥1.55.3॥

From her loining emerged radiant *Kāmbojas* like the Sun; from her udders, *Paplavas* armed with weapons; from her womb, *Yavanas*; from her anus, *Śakas*; and from her hair follicles, *Mlecchas*, *Haritas*, and *Kirātas*.

This episode vividly illustrates the yogic principle of *bhūta-jaya*—mastery over elemental forces—manifested through *Kāmadhenu*'s ability to generate entire warrior races from every part of her being.

The Ability to Assume Any Form (Kāmarūpa Siddhi)

There are several instances in the Rāmāyaṇa where the ability to change one's physical form is described. This siddhi (supernatural capability) can be understood as a result of intense yogic practice and tapas (austerity). The basis of this from *PYS* is thus explained:

कायेन्द्रियसिद्धिरशुद्धिक्षयात् तपसः ॥ 2.43 ॥

Perfection of the body and sense organs comes through the destruction of impurities by austerity.

Hanuman's expansion to evade capture

बाढमित्येव तां वाणीं प्रत्यगृह्णामहं ततः ।

आस्यप्रमाणादधिकं तस्या कायमपूरयम् ॥ 5.58.40॥

तस्या चास्यं महद्भूमिं वर्धते मम भक्षणे ।

न च मां सा तु बुबुधे मम वा विकृतं कृतम् ॥5.58.41॥

I said 'so be it' and then enlarged my body to a size greater than her mouth could hold. As she widened her huge and terrifying mouth to devour me, she did not realize that I had already taken on a massive, distorted form. This incident with *Surasā* showcases *Hanumān*'s power to instantly assume a different form—a clear case of *kāmarūpa siddhi* resulting from yogic mastery.

Hanuman Shrinking His Body

From the Sundara Kāṇḍa of the Campū Rāmāyaṇa

तनुं तनूकृत्य तदा हनूमान् कृत्वा प्रवेशं जठरे तदीये ...॥

Then *Hanumān* made his body extremely small and entered her (*Surasā*'s) stomach. This shows his mastery over the body—both expansion and contraction at will—hallmarks of *kāmarūpa siddhi*.

तपःस्वाध्यायेश्वरप्रणिधानानि क्रियायोगः ॥ 2.1 ॥

Austerity, study of scriptures, and surrender to God constitute *Kriyā Yoga*.

समाधिभावनार्थः क्लेशतनूकरणार्थश्च ॥ 2.2 ॥

(Kriya Yoga is practiced) for cultivating Samadhi and reducing afflictions.

Mārīca's Transformation into a Golden Deer

मुहूर्तदिव ददृशे मुहुर्दूरात्प्रकाशते ॥ 3.44.7 ॥

दर्शनादर्शनादेवं सोऽपाकर्षत राघवम्।

सुदूरमाश्रमस्यास्य मारीचो मृगतां गतः ॥ 3.44.8 ॥

Mārīca, having taken the form of a deer, appeared now near, now far. Through this illusion of vanishing and reappearing, he lured *Rāma* far from the hermitage. Unlike *Hanumān*, *Mārīca*'s *siddhi* stemmed from *tapas* driven by fear and compulsion—not from spiritual discipline or purification. Thus, while he possessed shape-shifting powers, he remained bound by karma and daiva (destiny).

***Rāma*'s Questions and *Vasiṣṭha*'s Responses**

On the Nature of the *Manas*

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Nirvāṇa Prakaraṇa, Sarga 2.19

मनो माया मितं द्वैतं मन एव सदा जगत्।

मनः संसारचक्रस्य कारणं मोक्षहेतुकम्॥

The mind is the illusion, the limited duality; the mind itself is the world. The mind alone is the cause of the cycle of worldly existence and also the means to liberation. *Rāma* expresses deep philosophical inquiry, questioning the nature of experience and existence—hallmarks of the contemplative seeker.

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Nirvāṇa Prakaraṇa 2.21

चित्तमेव हि संसारः तज्जयात् जायते जयः।

तच्च विज्ञेयमेकान्तात् यत्नतः शम्यते बुधैः॥

The mind itself is *saṃsāra*; conquering the mind leads to true victory. Therefore, the wise strive to fully understand and calm the mind. Here, *Vasiṣṭha* emphasizes that the mind's control or agitation determines bondage or freedom. Mental mastery is not optional, it is essential.

On Suffering and the *Saṃsāra*

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Vairāgya Prakaraṇa, Sarga 14.5

किं सुखं किं च दुःखं के च बन्धा विमोचनाः।

कोऽयं संसार इत्येवं चिन्तयामि मुहुर्मुहुः॥

What is happiness? What is suffering? What constitutes bondage and liberation? What is this *saṃsāra*? Thus do I constantly ponder again and again. Thus, *Rāma* expresses deep philosophical inquiry, questioning the nature of experience and existence—hallmarks of the contemplative seeker.

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Vairāgya Prakaraṇa 15.3

बन्धो हि नाम चित्तस्य स्पन्दनं द्वैतवासना।

मोक्षः शमसमायोगः स्वात्मन्येव विलयनम्॥

Bondage is nothing but the vibration of the mind caused by the tendency of doubting. *Mokṣa* is the total calming of the mind and its merging into *Paramātmā*.

About Yoga Discipline

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Nirvāṇa Prakaraṇa, Sarga 5.1

योगः किं किमनात्मानं किं स्वरूपं सदा भवेत्।

किं कर्तव्यं मया तात तनु मामुपदिश्यताम्॥

What is Yoga? What is the non-self? What is the eternal nature of reality? What should I do? O father (*Vasiṣṭha*), please instruct me thoroughly.

Rāma humbly seeks guidance from *Vasiṣṭha*, highlighting the classic *guru-śiṣya* relationship foundational to yogic inquiry.

Yoga Vāsiṣṭha, Nirvāṇa Prakaraṇa 5.4

योगो हि चित्तस्य स्थैर्यं चित्ते चात्मनि लीयते।

निःस्पन्दं स्थितिमाप्नोति तदैव योग उच्यते॥

Yoga is the steadiness (*sthairya*) of the mind. When the mind merges into the Self (*Ātman*) and becomes motionless, that alone is called *Yoga*. In these teachings, *Vasiṣṭha* establishes the mind (*manas, citta*) as the root of both bondage and liberation. Suffering arises from its movements; liberation is attained by its calming and merging into the *ātman*. The practice of Yoga is nothing but this inward journey of stilling the mind and recognizing one's true nature.

A Yogic Invocation to the Sun: *Āditya Hṛdayam*

As *Rāma* prepares to confront *Rāvaṇa* on the battlefield (in *Yuddha Kāṇḍa*), he is momentarily fatigued. At this pivotal moment, the sage *Agastya* approaches and blesses him by explaining the *Āditya Hṛdayam*, a sacred hymn dedicated to the Sun God which is revered for its power to dispel negativity and instill courage and clarity.

दैवतैश्च समागम्य द्रष्टुमभ्यागतो रणम् ।

उपागम्याब्रवीद्राममगस्त्यो भगवानृषिः ॥ २॥

The practice of reciting the *Āditya Hṛdayam* encompasses several yogic aspects:

Dhyāna (Meditation): *Rāma* is instructed to concentrate deeply on the Sun, exemplifying the *dhyāna* that is central to *Rāja Yoga*.

Mantra Japa (Chanting): The repetitive recitation of the hymn serves as a form of *mantra* meditation, aligning the mind and spirit.

Bhakti (Devotion): The hymn reflects a deep sense of devotion, a key aspect of *Bhakti Yoga*,

fostering a connection with the divine.

Prāṇāyāma (Breath Control): Though not explicitly detailed, the rhythmic recitation of verses naturally involves regulated breathing, aligning it with *prāṇāyāma*.

Yogic Attributes in Sītā's Character

Although *Sītā Devī* is not depicted as practicing formal *yoga* techniques, her character throughout the *Rāmāyaṇa* reflects key yogic qualities.

Emotional Mastery: She remains composed through intense trials, demonstrating *śama* (tranquility) and *dhṛti* (fortitude).

Inner Purity: Her unwavering chastity and refusal to yield to *Rāvaṇa* reflect *śuddhatva* (purity).

Bhakti : Her constant remembrance and love for *Rāma*, even in separation, epitomize *Bhakti Yoga*.

Mental Discipline: *Sītā* exhibits *manonigraha* (control of the mind), a core requirement for both *Jñāna* and *Vairāgya*.

Inner strength during the abduction: When *Rāvaṇa* abducts *Sītā*, she exhibits extraordinary emotional resilience and unwavering inner focus. Despite the trauma and fear of her situation, she maintains her composure, resists depression, and constantly contemplates *Rāma* through prayer and inward meditation. This sustained mental discipline reflects the yogic practices.

महागिरिमिवाकम्प्यं महेन्द्रसदृशं पतिम्।

महोदधिमिवाक्षोभ्यमहं राममनुव्रता॥3.47.33॥

I am devoted to Rama, my husband, who is unshakeable like a huge mountain, is comparable to Lord Indra and is imperturbable like the mighty ocean.

Sītā's devotion in *Aśoka-vana*

As a response to *Rāvaṇa*'s multiple attempts to persuade *Sītā* to become his queen, this was one of the responses given by *Sītā Devī* to him.

शक्या लोभयितुं नाहमैश्वर्येण धनेन वा॥5.21.15॥

अनन्या राघवेणाहं भास्करेण प्रभा यथा।

I cannot be lured by your power or wealth. I am inseparable from *Rāghava*, like the radiance from the sun. This verse vividly illustrates *Sītā*'s steadfast commitment and spiritual bond with *Rāma*, emphasizing her exclusive *bhakti*.

Agni Pariksha – Sita's Purity and Power Through Yogic Discipline

In the *Yuddha Kāṇḍa*, after *Rāvaṇa*'s defeat, *Sītā* undergoes the *Agni Parīkṣā* (trial by fire), a moment that affirms her purity and spiritual strength. Emerging unharmed from the flames, she

demonstrates her mastery of inner self-control, purity (*śuddhatva*), and truthfulness (*satya*), the key yogic virtues.

यथामांशुद्धचरितांदुष्टांजानातिराघवः ।

तथालोकस्यसाक्षीमांसर्वतःपातुपावकः ॥6.119.26॥

If in *Rāma*'s view, I am of impeccable conduct and so also if what he is seeing is not known to be true, let the world witness and Fire God protect me. Following this, *Sītā* steps into the fire, and *Agni*, the fire deity, emerges to present her unharmed, affirming her chastity and yogic mastery over the body, mind, and senses.

A Cosmic Union

Later, in the *Uttara Kāṇḍa*, *Sītā* prays to *Bhūmi Devī* (Mother Earth) to receive her back, if she has remained pure in thought and deed. *Uttara Kāṇḍa*, *Sarga* 110 –

nāhaṁ manasā pāpaṁ kiñcid eva samācare |
na cāpy anyam manasā me rāghavāt priyam ||
yadi satyam bravīmy etat satyena pṛthivi tvayā |
grhītāhaṁ samāyātum tvaṁ ca mām pratigṛhyatām ||

I have never committed any sin, even in thought, nor have I ever considered anyone other than *Rāghava* dear to me in my mind. If this is the truth, Oh Earth, may you receive me into yourself. Thus, at her words, the Earth opens up, and *Bhūmi Devī* embraces her, symbolically reclaiming a daughter of absolute purity.

Conclusion

The *Rāmāyaṇa*, *Pātañjala Yoga Sūtras*, and *Yoga Vāsiṣṭha*, though distinct in form and philosophical emphasis, together reveal a shared vision of yogic life rooted in discipline (*niyama*), inner purity (*śuddhatva*), and devotion (*bhakti*). From the narrative devotion of *Vālmīki* and the disciplined wisdom of *Nārada*, to the supernatural yogic abilities of *Hanūmān*, *Sampaṭi*, and *Kāmadhenu*, and finally to the profound inner strength and *sāttvic* radiance of *Rāma* and *Sītā*, each episode in the *Rāmāyaṇa* reflects the living spirit of *yoga*.

Patañjali's system outlines the mechanics and stages of *yoga* like *Kriyā-Yoga*, *Samyama*, and *Kaivalya*, while the *Yoga Vāsiṣṭha* delves into the depths of the mind (*citta*), illusion (*māyā*), and liberation (*mokṣa*). These philosophical structures find vivid embodiment in the *Rāmāyaṇa*'s characters, who lived it each according to their *dharma*.

Ultimately, these texts remind us that *yoga* is not confined to the *āsana* (mat) or the *guha* (cave),

but is a way of living, anchored in consciousness, unfolding through life's trials, and leading toward the highest realization (*paramārtha*).

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